

Addressing Special Educational Needs of Learners : A Profile

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ABSTRACT : This article is basically intended to highlight on the on-growing needs of the children with disabilities – needs which are rooted in their conceptual genesis as well as in their present psycho-social context. This article delineates an in-depth sermon that life is not a series of splendid lamps, symmetrically arranged; life is a hard reality to those who feel its existence in every fraction of a moment. The article speaks of the concept of special education, inclusive education, mainstreaming and their relevant impact on learners and society at large. Mainstreaming is obviously the sunshine, laden with clouds. Yet, it is the ultimate destination of the journey. Education of children with disabilities is a greater and more arduous challenge. “Where is the Life we have lost in living”? Still, the search for light will be continued.....

Keywords : Special education, inclusive education, mainstream education

**When I consider how my light is spent
Ere half my days, in this dark world and wide,
And that one talent which is death to hide
Lodged with me useless, though my soul more bent.**

The extract, taken from John Milton's 'On his blindness' is a pain-stricken odyssey that depicts the unrhythmed episode of life. At the same time, it portrays the rays of light in the canvas of darkness. Our search for light is started with a point-blank darkness; life is basically a rainbow which also includes black. There are children around us, our children to

whom either the physique or the psyche has become a great challenge, an insurmountable hurdle to cross. When a boy, visually impaired to the maximum extent by birth, asks his parents, "How does the sky look like?" "What about the sense of colours, the petallic arrangement of a rose?" All the answers in most cases become abstract – all the assistive devices suddenly become so ineffective that no language can be able to penetrate the pervasive darkness. Dream, sheer dream, mixed with reality and imagination becomes the only ambience. Soren Kierkegaard, the great existentialist, once opined.

“Life must be understood backwards ; but it must be lived forwards.” The conceptual genesis for the education with special needs had been emerged with such an emotional beckoning that reminds us the apt and profound advice of poet John Oxenham, “Share thy little with another !/ stretch a hand to one unfriended,.....”

It is true that in spite of having ‘the treasure within’, the immense potentialities, the children with special needs have often become an object of sympathy from the psycho-societal point of view. People with disabilities have a fundamental right to live and participate in the same setting and programmes — in schools, at home, in the workplace, and in the community — as do people without disabilities. Special education must continue to expand its efforts to recognize and respond appropriately to all learners with exceptional educational needs. Exceptional children includes children who experience difficulties in learning as well as those children whose performance is so superior that modifications in curriculum and instructions are necessary to help them fulfil their potential. Thus, ‘exceptional children’ is an inclusive term that refers to children with mental retardation, learning disabilities, emotional and behavioral disorders, communication (speech and language) disorders, hearing loss, blindness and low vision, physical and mental impairments, severe disabilities, intellectual giftedness and special talents. An individualized programme of specialised education is required to meet their needs. Thus, special education consists of purposeful intervention efforts at three different levels : preventive, remedial and compensatory. Successful interventions prevent, eliminate and overcome the obstacles that might keep an

individual with disabilities from learning and from full and active participation in school and society.

- Preventive — intervening to keep potential or minor problems from becoming a disability.
- Remedial — eliminating the effects of the disability through instructions.
- Compensatory — teaching the use of skills or devices that enable successful functioning in spite of the disability.

Special education is individually planned, specialized, intensive, goal-directed instruction.

It is very pertinent yet conscience - stricken affair that in independent India till the day, existing laws related to protection and education for the children with disabilities are not sufficient in general. We are still cling to more individualized and exclusive instruction that ultimately result in psycho-social isolation and exclusion of learners with special needs. The idea of inclusive education is thus gaining ground all over the world. Inclusive education or Integrated education is an education programme in which exceptional children attend classes with normal children in the same educational setting. Such a combination may be taken as social integration or academic integration or both. To enlarge the social consciousness to include the disabled into the mainstream in as many activities as possible, and to break the inner shell of the disabled to include the beautiful and wonderful world outside, erasing as much as possible their feeling of insufficiency or limitedness, or of being ‘different’, the idea of inclusive education in spite of its arduous challenge, is a must. The general education system is acknowledging the fact that

education of all types of children including that of children with disabilities should come under the purview of mainstream. In special school concept, the special education component is Apart from the general education system, whereas in integrated approach, it is A part of the general education. Inclusive education goes one step further. In this approach, the special education is an integral part of the general education system. Therefore, 'special school

concept' to 'Inclusive Education' can be treated as an evolutionary process in services for children with disabilities. Of course, there are two separate terms which are, very often, synonymously associated with 'integration'. These terms are — (i) Mainstreaming and (ii) Normalisation. Further impetus has been attached to it by the UNESCO World Conference on Education with special needs, held in Spain in 1994. The Conference considered the future direction of the special needs in the light of "Equalisation of educational opportunity" and "Education for all" movement. The fundamental interpretation of the word "Mainstreaming" is that it does not mean placement of all exceptional students in regular classes. Mainstreaming is the education of mildly challenged children in the regular classroom. It is a concept that is compatible with the least restrictive environment.

Democratic ethos and demands of human right perspectives necessitate equal treatment of each and every child with dignity and respect. At the same time, the teacher needs to recognise the individual differences the children bring to the school and help each of them develop and realise their potential leading to equal opportunity to succeed in life. This calls for inclusive education. The UNESCO report (1993) expressed: "Education has to face up to this problem (the problem of inequalities in education) now more than ever as a world society struggles painfully to be born: education is at the heart of both personal and community development; its mission is to enable each of us, without exception, to develop all our talents to the full and to realize our creative potential, including responsibility of our own lives and achievement of our personal aims." [Learning the Treasure within, 1998]

Schools in an inclusive classroom comprise all children with wide range of ability, learning experiences and background. It would be essential to respond to students with special educational needs from different sections of the society, especially, socially and economically disadvantaged groups. Their learning styles, pace of learning and motivations differ due to various psychological, sociological and economic reasons. Teachers need to have knowledge and skills to deal effectively with students with special needs. Educators are of the view that context specific models have to be prescribed for the education of children with disabilities. Teachers have to make sincere efforts to develop an environment that would generate self-motivated, self-actualising, self-monitored and self-reliant learning. The preparation of teachers

for learners with special educational needs requires more focussed objectives and corresponding content pedagogy and evaluation procedures. The NCFSE-2000 reiterates that the task of identifying the creative potentialities of the gifted and talented must be nurtured right from early childhood. Emotional care of the gifted and talented occupies an important place in transactional strategies. The total endeavour in this respect would be need-based.

Conclusion

The Dakar Declaration suggests that education for all children should be achieved by the year 2015. But the actual picture is not so encouraging. In spite of all out efforts the large number of the students with disabilities are not visible. Their enrollment in the regular schools have been limited and symbolic. Inclusion is not a privilege we are going to give to the children with disabilities, but it is the natural consequence of a humane society and it is also true that 'Education for all' can never be a reality without them. Government, community, administration, teacher, parents, professional must be equipped to face and inhibit the attitudinal obstacles that prevent the children with disability to be enrolled in regular classroom. Mainstreaming is not a fad or a slogan ; it is a workable process that needs a comprehensive support system for its success in the school. It is very much necessary that the pre-service teachers should get an overview of education of children with disabilities, their learning characteristics, methods of instructional strategies and evaluation procedures. Special teachers along with the general teachers who understand the concepts of educating children with disabilities can help them effectively in

classroom learning and in this process, education of these children will become an integral part of the overall system. So, education of children with disability will be a component in the training of educational planners and administrators as well as preservice and inservice teachers. District institutes of Education and Training (DIET), Colleges of Teacher Education (CTE) and the Institute of Advanced Study in Education (IASE) which have been provided with facilities for this component will have to pay particular attention to this aspect of teacher training. While drawing up schemes for strengthening SCERTs, cells for education of the handicapped may be considered as envisaged in Integrated Education for Disabled Children (IEDC). "Let them have the opportunity of learning the way they learn best. Bit by bit we can restore the lives of these children through alert and strong decisions at all levels to fully repair their educational paths through maintaining and extending our educational options, educationally appropriate instruction and the commitment to invest in our most valuable resources — our children, all of them". (McGrath, Johns & Mathur, 2004). So, if we stretch out our hands of love and cooperation to those unbloomed or blooming, they will obviously spread out the branches of their 'have' towards the sun. Let us hope to reach the unreached, to give a healthy balance to the unbalanced, to touch the sky with its limit.

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